

MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPLIANT WINGS TO HARVEST SOLAR ENERGY IN FLAPPING WING AIR VEHICLES

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Keywords: Multifunctional Compliant Wings, Robot Birds, Energy Harvesting

ABSTRACT

Robo Raven is a Flapping Wing Air Vehicle (FWAV) designed and developed at the University of Maryland. Like most ornithopters (aka, robot birds), this vehicle relies on compliant wing structures that deform the wings while flapping to generate the necessary forces for aerodynamic flight. To make sure the force generated by the wings is enough to maintain flight, the FWAVs are made from lightweight materials to minimize payload. This also limits the onboard energy available for the vehicle resulting in short flights. To extend the flight time of Robo Raven, flexible solar cells can be introduced throughout the vehicle to harvest energy from the sun while in and out of flight. Three Robo Raven III designs were created and characterized with solar cell integrated into the wings, body and tail of the original vehicle. More energy was harvested for the vehicle allowing for longer flights and for the vehicle to recharge without the use of a battery charger. However, the solar cells added mass and stiffness to the wings affecting flight performance. These changes in performance were characterized through load cell testing. Different tails were designed for maximum aerodynamic force generation. These tail designs were load cell tested and the best design was chosen. The resulting Robo Raven III V3 platform provided the longest flight out of any Robo Raven vehicle while still maintaining flight. Recently a hybrid version of Robo Raven, known as Robo Raven V, was developed with propellers that help the vehicle take off and gain more lift and thrust than previous versions. This version was combined with Robo Raven III to achieve improved performance and energy harvesting benefits in a single platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have been gaining popularity for many applications where an aerial view provides a situational advantage for the user [1-3]. On the smaller scale of UAVs, Flapping Wing Aerial Vehicles (FWAVs) draw inspiration from nature and imitate insect, bat, and bird flight. Depending on the design of the vehicle, the resulting flight can take positive aspects from both fixed wing and rotary flight. Many flapping wing platforms have already been designed, built, tested and modeled [3-22]. Designs inspired by bird and bat flight share some interesting characteristics. Observing the University of Delaware's ornithopter and Small & Big Bird developed at the University of Maryland, the wings are made up of thin stiff rods acting as a skeleton connected by a thin membrane that acts like a skin. The passive deformation of the wings while flapping up and down provide the vehicle with the aerodynamic forces necessary for flight. However, since these small vehicles need to be as lightweight as possible they are powered by small battery limiting the amount of time the vehicle can stay in flight. One way to increase the flight time of the vehicle is to harvest energy from the sun using solar cells. This supplemental source of power will allow the FWAV to stay in flight for a longer period of time as well as allow the vehicle to recharge outdoors between flights.

More recently, Robo Raven was developed at the University of Maryland [23]. This platform has wings controlled independently by Futaba S9352HV High Voltage Servo motors that can be programmed for more maneuverable flights. Like its predecessors, it also has a small battery limiting its flight endurance. However, the available surface area on the wings, body, and tail of the vehicle makes Robo Raven a perfect candidate for solar cell integration. Through the successful integration of solar cells, these structures become multifunctional in that they provide more than one function for the entire FWAV platform. Multifunctional structures have already been integrated into FWAVs. A Micro Air Vehicle (MAV) constructed with MEMS technology has a membrane made of a PVDF skin, allowing it to act as a real time load sensor to directly analyze flight performance [24]. Thomas et al. developed another MEMS-based insect-inspired flapping wing platform known as RoboBee uses artificial muscles to achieve novel controlled flight dynamics [25]. Thomas et. al. described the combination of structure and battery in the design of an electric-propelled UAV as an example of a multi-functional material system [26]. More recently at the University of Maryland, elastomeric strain gauges were placed on the wings of a flapping wing Micro Air Vehicle (MAV) [27]. These sensors captured deformations caused by flapping. The outputs from these sensors were directly correlated to thrust production which essentially made the wing into a skin-like structure. Extending these principles to the various structures of Robo Raven will increase vehicle endurance and overall system efficiency. The wings not only provide the vehicle with the aerodynamic forces necessary for flight but also provide electrical power for the vehicle. The tail which is responsible for generating the vehicle's pitch during regular flight and allows the FWAV to turn will also be supplying the vehicle with electrical power. The body which is normally just structural support will also provide the vehicle with electrical power. The increase in available energy is intended to increase the flight time of Robo Raven; however, the addition of mass and stiffness to the vehicle is expected to effect the performance of the vehicle. These effects must be found, characterized, and understood.

2 SOLAR CELL INTEGRATION TO THE WINGS

The original Robo Raven platform was developed in the Advanced Manufacturing Lab at the University of Maryland [23]. Unlike typical ornithopters that use a single motor to actuate both wings, Robo Raven uses two separate motors to actuate each wing individually. Robo Raven weighs 289 g with a wingspan of 114.3 cm. The original wing design was adapted from previous designs developed in AML

for smaller FWAVs [28-30]. The wing was comprised of a carbon fiber skeleton held together by a Mylar membrane. This geometry allows the wings to undergo a passive deformation that is crucial to endurance, speed, maneuverability, climbing, gliding, and other behaviors. Integrating solar cells into the wings do affect these capabilities; therefore, thin flexible solar cells were chosen to minimize these detrimental effects. The solar modules chosen for integration were Powerfilm's© MPT6-75 flexible solar cell modules. These flexible 7.3 x 11.4 cm solar cells are reported by the manufacturer to produce 50 mA of current at 6 V. However, these commercial modules came with an encapsulation that was too thick and stiffened the cells. By removing the encapsulation, the solar modules were thinner and less stiff, making them more compatible with the Mylar membrane.

The first Robo Raven III design consisted of 6 of these modules integrated to each wing. This 12 module design added 20.2 g to the vehicle, but generated an additional 3.6 Watts. The modules were first adhered to themselves to make a panel, then a rectangular section was cut from the Mylar to accommodate the panel to the front most part of the wing. The panel was adhered in place and was a part of the wing. This area was chosen because it undergoes the least amount of deformation while flapping. It has minimal effects on the overall performance of the wing. A flight test was conducted and it was determined that Robo Raven III V1 was capable of flight. An image of the completed Robo Raven III V1 design can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Robo Raven III V1 (left) and V2 (right)

In an attempt to generate the most power out of the wings as possible, Robo Raven III V2 was designed. This expanded on the previous version and included a second row of 5 more solar modules per wing. The additional stiffness added to the wing by the second row of solar modules restricted the amount of deformation the wing could undergo. The wing was slightly expanded and took on a teardrop shape to regain the lost deformation and produce enough force to stay in flight. A comparison of the two wings can be seen in Figure 2 and the completed Robo Raven III V2 platform can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Comparison of Robo Raven III V2 wings (left) vs. Robo Raven III V1 (right)

Load cell tests were conducted to compare the latest Robo Raven III V2 design to the original Robo Raven design. A test stand using a 6 DOF load cell was developed to hold the vehicle still while the forces generated by the FWAV were recorded. The test stand was placed at the end of a wind tunnel and the vehicle was positioned at a 20° incline to simulate actual flight conditions. The thrust and lift loads generated by each wing were recorded simultaneously. The time resolved results can be seen in Figure 3. The average values of lift and residual thrust can be seen in Table 1.

Ideally the residual thrust should average out to 0 g. The wind tunnel used creates a maximum velocity of 6 m/s. The actual flight velocity is 6.7 m/s. The actual payload was found experimentally to determine what the actual maximum flight weight and subsequent lift were. The payload capacity for Robo Raven during steady-state flight was measured to be 40 g, from which the scaling factor to determine the maximum flight weight from the measured lift and thrust was calculated to be 1.4X. Thus, the anticipated maximum flight weight could then be determined for each Robo Raven configuration using the scaling factor and force magnitude resolved from the lift and thrust measurements in Table 1, and is shown in Table 2.

The new design had an additional 56 g of mass to overcome compared to the original Robo Raven design. According to our results not only do we produce enough force to compensate for that increase in mass but we can even carry 21 more grams. The overall payload capability of the FWAV went down but is producing 0.36 N more than the original Robo Raven design.

Figure 3. Time resolved load cell comparison of Robo Raven designs.

Robo Raven		Robo Raven III V2	
Residual Thrust (g)	Lift (g)	Residual Thrust (g)	Lift (g)
107	208	79	248

Table 1. Average Lift and Residual Thrust Values.

	Robo Raven	Robo Raven III V2
Weight of UAV (g)	290	346
Measured Load Magnitude (g)	234	260
Maximum Flight Weight (g)	330	367
Calculated Payload Capacity (g)	40	21

Table 2. Weight and payload comparison of Robo Raven and Robo Raven III V2

An unexpected multifunctional aspect with the new wings was the new sensing capabilities. In observing the power production of the new solar celled wings, we observed the waveforms produced by the wings. Using a National Instrument’s USB-6009 Data Acquisition card, the voltage and current were simultaneously collected while flapping in sunlight. Multiplying these two signals together, the power produced by each wing design was found. The Robo Raven III V2 produced on average 7.42 W while flapping.

Figure 4. Percent change in power output versus thrust

By observing the percent change in power from the mean power produced, a double peak wave form was observed. This was similar to the thrust wave form observed from the load cell results, as seen in Figure 4. When the two signals were measured at the same time, the signals peaked in the same locations. Thus, this indicated that solar cells can be used to sense changes in thrust production. This change can be used to help with autonomous flight, since the FWAV would be able to respond to changes quicker than the operator.

3 SOLAR CELL INTEGRATION TO THE BODY & TAIL

Integration of solar cells into both the wings and tail are expected to have significant effects on the flight performance of the FWAV. However, integrating solar cells into the body should have a minimal effect on vehicle performance. The integration of solar cells into the body should simply add mass to the

system. The integration of solar cells into the body should not affect the force generation or aerodynamics of the wing and tail structures. To integrate solar cells to the body of the FWAV, two mounts were custom made out of Polyoxymethylene or Delrin®.

These were designed to attach to the body and hold 2 to 3 solar modules to integrate an additional 6 solar modules to the vehicle. The different tail designs can hold 3 to 4 modules depending on the design. A total of four designs were made to observe how changes in tail design affect the vehicle’s performance. We wanted to see how surface area and spread angle of the tail affect vehicle performance.

Each of the new tail designs were load cell tested under flight condition. The test stand was placed in the wind tunnel and the vehicle was pitched to 20°. The FWAV was then powered on and allowed to flap at 4 Hz. The average loads of generated by each tail design were observed and recorded. Figure 5 shows the results from each tail design.

Figure 5. Thrust (left) and lift (right) forces generated by different tail designs

The wider tails with a spread angle of 120° generated more lift while the taller skinnier tails had a profile that generated more thrust. The larger tails also provide more thrust and less lift than their smaller counterparts. With this information, tails can be better designed to fit the right application. We needed the largest amount of force to be generated. Tail 4 provided the most amount of total force and was chosen as the tail design for Robo Raven III V3. This final version of Robo Raven III consisted of 28 solar modules on the wings, body, and tail of the vehicle and can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Robo Raven III V3

4 RESULTS FOR ENERGY HARVESTING PERFORMANCE

Outdoor testing demonstrated the electrical benefits of adding solar cells to the wings, body, and tail of the vehicle. As seen in Table 3, the FWAV with 22 solar modules gained an additional 38 seconds of flight time while the FWAV with 28 solar modules produced 1.8 W more, and it was able to stay in flight for an additional 14 s. If they were to follow the trend of the already integrated solar cells, we would have seen an increase of 10 s. Since these solar modules are not changing position relative to the sun during the test and are not constantly being deformed, they are able to electrically outperform the solar modules integrated to the wings.

Flight Platform	Number of Solar Modules	Average Watts Produced	Flight Time (min)	% increase
Robo Raven	0	0	4:10	0
Robo Raven III V2	22	6.6	4:48	15.2
Robo Raven III V3	28	8.4	5:02	20.8

Table 3. Flight time results versus number of solar modules

Since this endurance test was conducted while the FWAV was flapping in place, the benefits of having a more efficient tail that produces greater aerodynamic forces cannot be observed. With a platform that generates forces more efficiently, less power is needed to obtain the same functionality as the less efficient system.

The recharging capability of the 28 module platform was compared to the capability of the 26 module platform. The total recharging time of the 22 module FWAV was 90 min. The 28 Module FWAV was able to recharge a depleted battery in 87 min. This was a slower recharging rate than was expected.

With a power increase of 1.8 W, which is a 27.7% increase to the previous version of Robo Raven IIIv2, the recharge time should have been faster than 87 min. However, this electrical experiment for the 28 module FWAV was accomplished during the winter time in Maryland where the 22 cell experiment was done in the summer. This means that not only are we usually getting less direct sunlight from the sun, the temperature is usually much colder than the rest of the year. Lithium Polymer batteries are affected by low temperatures causing vehicle performance and capacitance of the battery to decrease.

5 ROBO RAVEN V WITH SOLAR CELLS

Robo Raven V is the newest platform based off the original Robo Raven design produced at the University of Maryland. Using two Hacker Brushless A05-10S 12 Pole 4200kV Motors with Gemfan 5x4 5040 Propellers CW/CCW at the rear of the vehicle, this platform is capable of also taking off from the ground instead of being launched into the air. The propeller also provide a huge boost in thrust, and in turn lift, at higher speeds during flight driven by the motors with a rated power of 32 W at 7 V. To harvest energy on this platform to meet the extra demands of these motors that are on top of the average 37 W used by the programmable servo motors when flapping at 4 Hz, the multifunctional compliant wings with solar cells were also used, as seen in Figure 7. However, since so much additional aerodynamic force is introduced by the propellers, the wings do not need to deform as much as before. Previously, adding 5 more solar cell modules to the 6 module wing on Robo Raven III did not provide enough lift and thrust due to the increased rigidity, which necessitated increasing the area of the wing by adding a teardrop shape to the trailing edge of the wing. With Robo Raven V, an 11 module wing was capable of achieving

flight without increasing wing area. Table 4 shows that wing’s flight characteristics on Robo Raven III, as well as on the new Robo Raven V platform when it is flapping and using the DC motors with 100% power to drive the propellers. It is important to note that the additional thrust generated by the propellers required recalibration of the scaling factor, which was determined to be 1.89 when operating the motors at 100% power.

	Robo Raven	11 Module Wing on Robo Raven III	Robo Raven V	11 Module Wing on Robo Raven V
Weight of UAV (g)	290	331	427	468
Measured Load Magnitude (g)	234	232	330	324
Maximum Flight Weight (g)	330	327	624	613
Calculated Payload Capacity (g)	40	-4	197	145

Table 4. Capabilities of Robo Raven and Robo Raven V, as well as Robo Raven III and Robo Raven V with the 11 module wings that were previously incapable of flight indicating

The stiffer solar cell wings on Robo Raven V do not produce as much force as the original wings. The maximum flight weight is 11 g less than Robo Raven V. However, the wings still produce enough force to overcome the additional 41 grams added by the solar cells with an additional 145 grams of payload capacity available. This allows the FWAV to gain altitude and fly with the stiffer and heavier wings, plus carry additional equipment. Thus, it is now possible to use Robo Raven V to investigate the benefits of using heavier and stiffer wings with higher efficiency solar cells that may not have otherwise been capable of flight, while also investigating the benefits of dynamic shape control using independently programmable wings.

Figure 7. Robo Raven V with 11 module wings that were previously incapable of flight without modifying the wing design (left), and now capable of flight (right)

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the effects of integrating solar cells into the wings, body, and tail of a FWAV. The mechanics of the wings inherently change due to the increase in stiffness caused by the stiffer solar cells replacing the lightweight Mylar membrane. Adding solar cells makes these structures multifunctional and allows the wings to produce aerodynamic forces, produce electrical power, and sense changes in thrust during the flapping cycle.

Adding solar cells makes the wings less compliant. Adding compliant sections to the wings allows for the forces to be recovered. 12 module and 22 module wings were constructed flown and tested. Load cell tests were conducted to show the aerodynamic forces being produced by the final Robo Raven III V2 design and were compared to the forces produced by the original Robo Raven design. The increase in mass from the solar cells was still overcome by the amount of lift produced by the new design. The power output from the solar cells also correlated to the thrust force produced. This makes it possible to sense changes in thrust in real time.

Using the additional surface area provided by the body and the tail, 6 solar modules were added to the Robo Raven IIIv2 platform to achieve a total of 28 modules producing 8.4 W of power. Tails were designed with either 3 or 4 modules and/or with 90° and 120° angles of spread between the spars. It was found that where a wider tail will produce more lift and less thrust than a taller tail of the same surface area. Since the vehicle is at a 20° angle of attack during flight, the thrust generated by the flapping wings blows air back towards the tail. The wider tail is able to be more affected this blowback, since its tips are directly behind the wings while at a 20° angle of attack, resulting in more lift and less thrust.

The resulting Robo Raven III V3 design produced the most power, stayed in flight the longest amount of time, and charged the battery the quickest. Producing 8.4 W from 28 solar modules, this FWAV was able to flap for a total of 5 minutes and 2 seconds. This is more than a 20% increase from the original Robo Raven design. It was also able to recharge the battery in 87 minutes just using solar power.

Using the benefits of solar power with the newest vehicle produced in AML, Robo Raven V, we were able to fly with a wing that was previously incapable of flight. The added thrust and lift provided by the vehicles propellers allowed the new platform to fly with stiffer and heavier wings, and also allows for investigating the benefits of dynamic shape control using independently controlled wings with programmable servo motors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was sponsored by AFOSR grant FA9550-12-1-0158 with Dr. Byung-Lip “Les” Lee program manager. Opinions expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect opinions of the sponsors.

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